

Dealing with Hand-Eye Calibration in Large Robotic Workcells: the METRIC Dataset

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Abstract—In robotic workcells designed for human-robot collaboration, a camera system capable of providing the robot with precise information about its surroundings is essential. This condition not only safeguards the operator but also ensures an optimized and safe collaborative process. For this purpose an accurate hand-eye calibration is crucial, to precisely locate elements in the scene in relation to the robot base. This scenario presents various challenges, including the need for calibrating a large camera network using small calibration patterns. This paper outlines a comprehensive analysis of the limitations exhibited by state-of-the-art hand-eye calibration methods when applied in such demanding real-world scenarios.

Index Terms—Hand-eye calibration, human-robot collaboration, robotic workcells

I. INTRODUCTION

The term Human–Robot Collaboration (HRC) refers to collaborative processes involving both humans and robots working together to achieve a common goal, with the main purpose of alleviating the workload of human operators and increasing the efficiency of the processes. In HRC scenarios, a camera system plays a crucial role, as it enables real-time monitoring of the robot’s workspace, a key element for preventing robot movements that could potentially harm humans. To ensure safe and reliable operations, the cameras must precisely know the robot’s position in the workcell, which leads to accurate localization of the other objects or persons in the scene with respect to the robot itself. Such scenario requires an accurate hand-eye calibration. This is necessary to determine the exact geometric transformation of each camera with respect to the manipulator’s base, which is usually the main reference frame. This provides a single 3D reference frame shared by all sensors in the camera network. This process typically involves an optimization procedure that leverages the corner detection of a planar calibration pattern that is attached to the robot’s end-effector and moved to different positions in front of the sensors that surround the manipulator. The hand-eye calibration in a camera network within large robotic workcells, as the one illustrated in Fig. 1, presents two primary challenges: (i) the usage of a limited-size calibration pattern to move the robot without self-collisions; (ii) large distance of the cameras from the robot to monitor a wider area (i.e., the entire workcell).

In the literature, just a few hand-eye calibration approaches guarantee robustness and accuracy for these challenging sce-

Fig. 1. Large-scale workcell of the IASLab at UniPD, equipped with a Panda robot arm with a checkerboard attached to its end-effector, surrounded by four Intel RealSense Depth D455 cameras.

narios. Most state-of-the-art methods exhibit accuracy limitations and are acceptable for small robotic workcells where sensors are positioned at a maximum distance of 1 m from the robot arm. This limitation makes them unsuitable for larger robotic workcells designed for HRC, where a wide camera network is needed. Moreover, there is lack of public datasets to evaluate the performance of hand-eye calibration methods in such demanding scenarios. In this paper, we present a comprehensive dataset acquired in a robotic workcell aimed to human-robot collaboration, which represents an ideal testbed for evaluating the accuracy and the robustness of hand-eye calibration systems.

II. THE METRIC DATASET

The METRIC¹ dataset [1] was collected in the robotic workcell at the IASLab of the University of Padua, Italy—the setup is depicted in Fig. 1. In this data collection the robot’s end-effector was moved along a carefully pre-planned trajectory, covering most of the robot’s workspace in a hemispherical path and ensuring constant visibility of the calibration pattern for the cameras, as shown in Fig. 2. The images were collected in two workcells of different size, named small and large, covering an area of approximately 7 m² and 15 m², respectively. Each image collection was performed using three camera networks that differ in the sensor type used,

This research has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101006732.

¹The dataset is publicly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7976058>

Fig. 2. Waypoints of the hemispherical planned trajectory.

namely Intel RealSense Lidar camera L515, Intel RealSense Depth D455 sensor and Microsoft Kinect V2 (only one type of sensor was used at a time). These images proved to be an excellent testbed for assessing the robustness of state-of-the-art calibration methods in a real-world HRC scenario with different camera network configurations and with various sensor resolution and field of view (FoV).

To evaluate the accuracy of the calibration methods, we computed the average translation error (μ_t) and rotation error (μ_θ). This was done evaluating the difference between the estimated geometric transformations of each camera relative to the robot base and their corresponding ground truth values, as follows:

$$\mu_t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (e_t)_i}{N} \quad \mu_\theta = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (e_\theta)_i}{N} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of cameras, $e_t = \|t - \hat{t}\|_2$ and $e_\theta = \text{angle}(R^T \hat{R})$, t and R correspond to the translation vector and rotation matrix obtained from the ground truth data, while \hat{t} and \hat{R} are the corresponding estimated values.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The assessment of the robustness of state-of-the-art calibration methods involved a comparison of four calibration algorithms from the literature: i) Evangelista’s unified algorithm [2]; ii) Tabb’s method [3], iii) Shah’s method [4]; and iv) Li’s method [5]. This comparison was carried out using the metrics outlined in (1). Tests were performed using both workcells. The results of the hand-eye calibration are specified in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
AVERAGE TRANSLATION AND ROTATION ERROR IN THE SMALL WORKCELL.

Method	Kinect V2		Depth D455		LiDAR L515	
	μ_t [mm]	μ_θ [deg]	μ_t [mm]	μ_θ [deg]	μ_t [mm]	μ_θ [deg]
Evangelista	42.79	0.57	45.14	0.43	26.20	0.39
Tabb	51.57	0.73	63.98	1.36	34.59	0.94
Li	66.67	0.73	51.03	0.72	23.70	0.31
Shah	27.22	0.75	23.90	0.54	18.51	0.34

In general, the narrower field of view of the LIDAR camera and the higher resolution of the Kinect V2 yielded superior calibration accuracy with respect to the Depth D455 camera. In

TABLE II
AVERAGE TRANSLATION AND ROTATION ERROR IN THE LARGE WORKCELL (A DASH DENOTES THE NON-CONVERGENCE OF THE ALGORITHM).

Method	Kinect V2		Depth D455		LiDAR L515	
	μ_t [mm]	μ_θ [deg]	μ_t [mm]	μ_θ [deg]	μ_t [mm]	μ_θ [deg]
Evangelista	77.26	0.77	136.39	1.33	60.59	0.43
Tabb	105.01	0.75	153.2	1.74	75.33	0.77
Li	129.39	0.72	—	—	26.39	0.30
Shah	54.92	0.73	—	—	26.15	0.31

the small workcell, Shah’s method provided greater robustness compared to the other methods. However, in the large workcell, Evangelista’s method exhibited the highest robustness to outliers, while Shah’s and Li’s optimization processes failed to converge on images collected using the Depth D455 camera network. The convergence failure can be mainly due to the sensitivity of their optimization process, relying on the Perspective-n-Point algorithm to estimate the camera-to-calibration-pattern transformation. The PnP algorithm operates by estimating this transformation using a set of 3D points in a single image. This approach can be vulnerable to inaccuracies, particularly when dealing with blurred images, negatively impacting the entire hand-eye calibration process, as evidenced by the experimental results. Conversely, alternative methods like Evangelista’s and Tabb’s, relying on the minimization of the reprojection error, successfully achieved convergence even with the Depth D455 camera, although with low accuracy, proving to be more robust against outliers.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a dataset that can be used as a valuable resource for evaluating the robustness of various hand-eye calibration methods, particularly with respect to two critical factors: i) the type of sensor used, and ii) the scale of the robotic workcell. Based on our analysis on this dataset, we have highlighted the main limitations of state-of-the-art hand-eye calibration methods applied on such real-world scenarios. Furthermore, we have provided a benchmark allowing researchers to compare and evaluate the effectiveness of their future calibration works against the results presented in this work.

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